

PROBLEMS OF MODERN PHILOLOGY

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Abstract: This article provides information about several pressing issues observed in contemporary philology. It discusses the annual evolution of language, the gradual obsolescence of literary language, and various difficulties encountered in translation. Furthermore, the daily advancements in language and modern technology are increasingly influencing contemporary philology, literary studies, and linguistics. The article analyzes topics such as the transformation of teaching methods, modern and innovative approaches to text analysis and translation, and the role of philologists in society. The article concludes by addressing solutions to modern philological problems and the findings of research in this field.

Keywords: contemporary philology, modern technology, cultural heritage, new words in articles, fairy tales, literature, scientific works, modern poems

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola zamonaviy filologiya fanida kuzatilayotgan bir qator dolzarb muammolar haqida ma'lumot beradi. Unda tilning yildan yilga yangilanishi, adabiy tilning tobora eskirishi hamda tarjimonlikdagi bir qancha qiyinchiliklarga duch kelishi aytib o'tiladi. Shuningdek, til va zamonaviy texnologiyalarning kun sayin rivojlanib borishi zamonaviy filologiyaga, adabiyotshunoslikka va tilshunoslikka o'z ta'sirini o'tkazib borayotgani qayd etiladi. Maqolada o'qitish metodlarining transformatsiyasi, matnlarni tahlil va tarjima qilishning zamonaviy, yangicha yondashuvlari, filologlarning jamiyatdagi roli kabi masalalar tahlil qilinadi. Maqola yakunida zamonaviy filologiyaga yechim hamda tadqiqotlardagi natijalar haqida so'z boradi.

Kalit so'zlar: Zamonaviy filologiya, zamonaviy texnologiyalar, madaniy meros, maqolalardagi yangi so'zlar, ertaklar, adabiyot, ilmiy ishlar, zamonaviy she'rlar.

In the era of modern globalization, the 21st century, it is important to preserve cultural heritage and communicate properly while preserving our language, which contributes to the beauty of our speech. Language is not only a means of communication between two people, but also the main function of language is to understand our identity and consciousness, to understand our words and actions, and to transmit values from generation to generation. Nowadays, the development of information technologies has had an impact on modern philology. The change in language from year to year, the use of new words in articles, fairy tales, literature, scientific works, modern poems, and expressions, is having a stronger impact.

The article examines the impact of a number of translation difficulties on modern philology. The final part of the article discusses a number of proposals and ideas for the development of modern philology and the solution of problems.

Reasons for the renewal of modern philology:

-Technology, globalization, information, exchange language changes

Variants of social language:

-Dialect, a variation of speech in society

The role of philologists:

-The fact that national traditions and customs have entered society through language and literature, through our speech

On top of that, we see that society forgets old words and, as a result, they are no longer used. The emergence of new words, in particular, brings with it a number of challenges for our translators. On the other hand, the ease of translation in modern philology is only due to the technological advantages of the internet but we face unique challenges in analyzing, processing, and storing data.

The language of each country is in constant flux and changes from year to year. The media, television, radio, social networks, and the communication between people in society unfortunately have little impact on our speech, that is, our literary language. Our philologists are asking themselves a number of questions. Many scholars are still pondering how to properly evaluate the new words that appear in our language. It seems that we need to adapt the eternal language to the people of the 21st century in a modern way, or to always maintain a balance between the two. I think that studying these problems is not only for linguists and philologists, but also for society as a whole. For example, how many millennia have passed since the pyramids in Egypt appeared? But only about 30 percent of the inscriptions on the walls of the pyramids are still intact. Let's imagine that we are living in 2025, but in 100 years, that is, a century, the world's population may not use even 50% of the words we use in our current communication by the year 3025. The reason is that times are changing and the life we live is changing, new words are entering our speech every day and old ones are leaving. The translation process is considered one of the most complex tasks, especially when translating idioms from one language into another. In such a situation, although automatic translation plays an important role for us at the moment, the human factor plays a much more important role in translation than automatic translation.

The emergence of modern philology does not mean that poverty has negative aspects, but it also led to the development of electronic libraries for the automatic storage and analysis of texts. In such cases, innovations are emerging, and new methods are being used in teaching science, rather than traditional methods. For example, interactive games, project-based learning, role play, case studies, and many other innovations have emerged, resulting in a much faster organization of students' information acquisition. The younger generation is

making a significant contribution to the development of their scientific potential. Modern philological education is also changing with the times.

In conclusion, this article addresses and attempts to resolve a number of problems in modern philology. The impact of digital technology on language, which has solved several problems in the field of translation, is considered one of the most important issues in today's philology. Current research shows that literary language has a great influence on modern linguistics. So, the only way to get rid of these problems is to increase the number of strong philologists, cadres, and translators who are highly educated. We hope that in the future; similar problems will be solved by philologists adapting to the changing demands of society. Language and philology also remain an important foundation for human development in communication.

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